

Spatiotemporal analysis of landscape dynamics and their use as input for the design of a habitat suitability index: A case study of *Oryctolagus cuniculus* in a Mediterranean region

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ABSTRACT

The connectivity of landscapes is increasingly threatened by urban sprawl, which leads to the fragmentation of habitats and thus endangers the species that live there. To address this situation, landscape dynamics in the literature have mostly been analyzed using predefined land cover classes, which were then not used to assess habitat suitability, but instead relied on physical variables. As a bridge between both aspects, this study aimed to model the spatiotemporal patterns of landscape fragmentation by analyzing the landscape metrics associated with four land cover groups classified according to their naturalness. Landscape metrics were then combined with a range of terrain, climate and proximity variables to develop a Habitat Suitability Index (HSI) for terrestrial animal species. The proposed methodology was tested using a case study in the Mediterranean region of the Valencian Community (Spain): landscape dynamics were assessed over the period 1992–2015, while the HSI was tested with the European rabbit (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) as the target species. The results obtained in terms of landscape dynamics showed a growing presence of artificial surfaces at the expense of fewer transformed areas, which became progressively fragmented over time. Moreover, the results of the developed HSI were highly concordant with observations of rabbit abundance in the region, based in particular on variables related to the temperature in the area and the patch shape in the preferred habitats of this species. These outputs can be used to support the implementation of habitat restoration strategies aimed at increasing ecological connectivity through measures such as wildlife crossings.

1. Introduction

Global development continues to be significantly shaped by globalization processes, a growing population, increasing urbanization, and climate change. The consequences of these processes are particularly evident in the change in biodiversity (McDonald et al., 2019): increasing connectivity and global trade promote the spread of invasive species at the expense of native or endemic species, while the expansion of built-up areas and infrastructure destroys habitats. An increasing number of rare species are now threatened with extinction because their habitats are being destroyed, fragmented, or reduced (Ntshanga et al., 2021).

This is due to ongoing transformations of the landscape toward increasingly unnatural environments. Human interventions in land use patterns lead to habitat fragmentation and, consequently, the endangerment of species (Powers and Jetz, 2019). The extent of this landscape fragmentation can vary, posing a threat not only to the species living

directly within it but also impacting the ecosystem services provided by these habitats and their positive effects on humans (Zhao et al., 2019).

To model this fragmentation, it is convenient to study the spatiotemporal changes in land cover over a long period to analyze their extent. To this end, there have been numerous studies that, in addition to mapping these spatiotemporal changes, also attempted to identify their respective driving factors (Dimobe et al., 2017; Gbanie et al., 2018; Hermosilla-Palma et al., 2021; Muhammed and Elias, 2021), including intensive land management, tourism, wildlife, decline in forest cover and increase in built-up area. In addition, some studies address fragmentation in specific habitats or landscape types, such as farmlands (Xu et al., 2023), wetlands (Alaei et al., 2022; Dutra et al., 2023) or specific woody plant communities (Kumi et al., 2021), while others focused on the effects of land use change on existing ecosystem services (Biswas et al., 2023; Li and Zhang, 2023).

The effects of such landscape changes in terms of habitat alteration

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have been investigated in the literature through the development of Habitat Suitability Indices (HSI). Most of these indices are species-specific, assessing the studied landscapes based on various topographical, climatic, distance and land cover parameters and dividing them into different suitability classes. Given the spatial component inherent in habitat suitability modelling, the analytical methods used to derive such indices often rely on Geographic Information Systems (GIS) to produce georeferenced data. Then, these data are handled using different approaches ranging from statistical tools such as principal component analysis (Prasetyo et al., 2017) or logistic regression (Jung et al., 2016; Paudel et al., 2015), machine learning algorithms in the form of species distribution models like the Maximum Entropy (MaxEnt) model (Wilting et al., 2010) and deep neural networks (Rew et al., 2020), or Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) (Goparaju et al., 2017).

Among the above methods, MCDA stands out for its simplicity, which increases its usability for non-experts in complex numerical tools. MCDA serves to find the best compromised alternative to complex problems characterized by multiple conflicting criteria and where there may not be a solution that meets all of these requirements simultaneously (Chakraborty et al., 2023). In this context, the alternatives are the zones into which the study area is divided and based on which a series of parameters or criteria are calculated so that their joint consideration helps to identify locations that are better suited to certain species in terms of habitat. As such, the development of HSI models falls within the assessment of supporting ecosystem services aimed at biodiversity and habitat protection. The versatility of MCDA methods could allow the results of a HSI to be combined with similar models to assess other ecosystem services, such as prioritizing rainwater harvesting sites, locating urban heat-prone areas, or determining where the health benefits of ecosystems are greatest.

Previous works on spatiotemporal analysis of landscape dynamics have focused on the patterns of specific land covers as defined in their data sources; however, there is a lack of approaches to address the issue from the perspective of the degree of naturalness associated with such land cover types. Furthermore, the creation of HSI is based primarily on physical factors, including topographic, distance-based and, at most, climate variables, with landscape variables less often used to analyze an area's suitability for supporting wildlife.

At this point, this study sought to address the identified research gaps. Therefore, the aim was to model the spatiotemporal patterns of

landscape dynamics by considering various landscape metrics calculated for different land cover groups classified according to their naturalness. Additionally, a MCDA-based HSI applicable to both common and endangered terrestrial animal species was developed by coupling commonly used physical variables with landscape metrics. The usefulness of the developed methods was tested using the Valencian Community (Eastern Spain) as a case study and the European rabbit (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) as the target species.

2. Methodology

The proposed methodology was approached as depicted in Fig. 1. The landscape dynamics in the Valencian Community were analyzed by grouping the land cover classes in the region into four categories according to their degree of naturalness. A range of landscape metrics was used to identify key trends in landscape fragmentation over time. With this global picture of the situation in the region, the focus was then placed on the habitat conditions of a specific species such as the European rabbit (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*). Hence, the landscape metrics corresponding to this species were coupled with a series of climate, terrain and proximity indicators to develop a Habitat Suitability Index (HSI) using Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) methods.

2.1. Case study and data preparation

The Valencian Community is a region in the east of the Spanish Peninsula (Fig. 2a). It covers an area of 23,255 km² and is home to 5,058,138 people (INE, 2021). The region is characterized by a Mediterranean climate, which, however, varies in the three provinces that make up it: temperate conditions prevail in Valencia and Castellón, while Alicante, to the south, is drier (Beck et al., 2018).

The dynamics of *Oryctolagus cuniculus* in the region are mixed, with overpopulation affecting crops in some areas and disappearance of the species occurring in others (Generalitat Valenciana, 2022) (Fig. 2b). According to the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Red List (Smith and Boyer, 2006), this animal, native to the Iberian Peninsula (Spain), is endangered worldwide and near threatened at the European level. The reasons for this decline are myxomatosis, rabbit hemorrhagic disease, hunting and habitat loss (Santoro et al., 2023). The controversy surrounding this species reinforces the interest in analyzing

Fig. 1. Concept map of the proposed methodology for analyzing landscape dynamics and deriving a Habitat Suitability Index (HSI).

Fig. 2. (a) Location map of the study area, (b) Observations of European rabbit in 2015 and ESA CCI land cover maps for (c) 1992 and (d) 2015.

its distribution in terms of habitat suitability.

The main data needed to analyze landscape fragmentation is land cover. Due to the location of the study area, three sources were identified: Corine Land Cover (CLC) (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, 2015), European Space Agency Climate Change Initiative (ESA CCI) (ESA, 2010) and the Information System on Land Occupation in Spain (SIOSE) (MITMA, 2022). The latter was discarded due to the complexity of its codification and geographic limitation, hampering the reproducibility of the proposed approach out of Spain. The CLC maps are valid for all of Europe and have a good resolution; however, their production is not homogeneous and relies on different procedures, which can lead to uncertain results (García-Álvarez and Camacho Olmedo, 2017). Although the ESA CCI maps have a coarser resolution (300 m), they are global and cover a longer period (1992–2015). Therefore, they were considered the best option for this study. The 1992 and 2015 ESA CCI maps for the Valencian Community are shown in Fig. 2c and d.

The ESA CCI land cover maps are also the recommended source for calculating Land Cover Naturalness (LCN) according to Vollmer et al. (2018). The LCN assigns a score to different land cover types depending on the degree of landscape transformation. Therefore, the LCN scores were crossed with the ESA CCI codes to result in Table 1. Furthermore, the ESA CCI codes were classified based on the LCN weights into four groups as follows: 1 – Completely artificial (LCN ≤ 10), 2 – Transformed system (30 ≤ LCN ≤ 50), 3 – Cultural assisted system (60 ≤ LCN ≤ 70) and 4 – Natural and semi-natural (LCN = 100) (FHI, 2022).

The distribution of *Oryctolagus cuniculus* in the Valencian Community was determined using data from 2015, the last year covered by the ESA CCI maps. These data came from the records of the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF, 2022), a global archive that provides open data on beings of the seven kingdoms of life on Earth. Observations recorded by GBIF in the region were cured to eliminate records with

Table 1

Proposed correspondence between Land Cover Naturalness (LCN) weights and ESA CCI land cover types.

Land Cover Naturalness (LCN) score	ESA CCI code	ESA CCI description
NA	0	No Data
0	190	Urban areas
10	150	Sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)
	151	Sparse tree (<15%)
	152	Sparse shrub (<15%)
	153	Sparse herbaceous cover (<15%)
	190	Bare areas
	200	Consolidated bare areas
	201	Unconsolidated bare areas
30	20	Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding
40	10	Cropland, rainfed
	11	Herbaceous cover
	12	Tree or shrub cover
60	30	Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<50%)
70	40	Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)
	100	Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)
	110	Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%) / tree and shrub (<50%)
	160	Tree cover, flooded, fresh or brackish water
	170	Tree cover, flooded, saline water
	180	Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brackish water
100	50	Tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)
	60 (61, 62)	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
	70 (71, 72)	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)
	80 (81, 82)	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
	90	Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needleleaved)
	120	Shrubland
	(121,122)	Grassland
	130	Lichens and mosses
	140	Water bodies
	210	Permanent snow and ice
	220	

missing or uncertain fields (Chamberlain, 2016). Fig. 2b depicts the cleaned records of *Oryctolagus cuniculus* in the Valencian Community for 2015.

The purpose of this part of the investigation was to model the density of observations of European rabbits using several inputs as listed in Table 2, so that the main factors driving their presence or absence could be identified. These data were proposed based on the recommendations in the literature on this rabbit species in the context of the study area (Gálvez-Bravo, 2017).

Although the origins of these data ranged from regional to global sources, they were all consistent in their reproducibility on a global scale. Climate data for historical and climate change projections is provided by e.g. WorldClim (Fick and Hijmans, 2017), while a Digital Elevation Model (DEM) with a resolution of 30 m can be acquired from the Copernicus program (ESA, 2023). The soil type can be found on the hydrogeological map of the Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources (Duscher et al., 2015). Vector data on roads and hunting are available from the OpenStreetMap initiative, whereas landscape metrics can be determined from ESA CCI land cover maps, as previously mentioned.

Climate data were used without further processing as representative of the effects of extreme temperatures and precipitation on rabbit

Table 2

Key characteristics of the datasets used to analyze landscape dynamics and derive a Habitat Suitability Index (HSI).

Data	Date	Format	Resolution/ Scale	Source	Variable short names
Maximum temperature	2015	NetCDF	0.1 degrees	(Gutiérrez et al., 2019)	tasmx
Precipitation	2015	NetCDF	0.1 degrees	(Gutiérrez et al., 2019)	pr
Digital Elevation Model (DEM)	2018	ASCII	25 m	(ICV, 2022)	slope
Roads	2023	Shapefile	1:5000	(ICV, 2022)	roads
Lithostratigraphic map	2009	Shapefile	1:100,000	(del Pozo Gómez, 2009)	soil
Hunting areas	2012	Shapefile	1:5000	(ICV, 2022)	hunt
Landscape metrics	2015	RasterLayer	300 m	(ESA, 2010)	area, cai, circle, contig, core, enn, frac, grate, ncore, para, perim, shape

distribution (Gonçalves et al., 2002). Because these were the inputs available at the coarsest resolution, their pixels were used to create a grid in terms of which the other data were expressed. In other words, the remaining variables were calculated as statistics (mean or sum) per climate pixel. Expressing different variables as statistics per pixel has been found to be effective at a similar spatial scale for combining data at different resolutions (Jato-Espino et al., 2022). In the case of the observations of European rabbits, this was preceded by the calculation of their associated utilization density, which indicates the relative frequency of occurrence of this animal (Worton, 1989).

It has been argued that rabbits prefer altitudes below 1200–1500 m (Fa et al., 1999); however, since the study area is at a lower elevation, the DEM was not directly used. Instead, the mean slope per pixel was determined as a derived product of the DEM. The data on the spatial distribution of road axes, provided as a vector layer, was transformed into raster format to determine the mean distance from each pixel to the nearest road. Both altitude and road distance have been argued to be negatively associated with the presence of rabbits (Tapia et al., 2014).

The type of soil is important as it needs to be dry, well-drained, light and loose (Parer and Libke, 1985). The lithostratigraphic map used included a field with an assessment of the permeability of the soils in the area ranging from “very low” to “very high” that was used as a proxy for these characteristics. Therefore, soil suitability was assumed to be proportional to permeability, so the following scoring scale was used: very low – 0.00, low – 0.25, medium – 0.50, high – 0.75 and very high: 1.00. Once these values were set, they were converted into raster format to enable determining the mean scores per climate pixel.

Processing the hunting areas was simpler as these zones only had to be transformed into raster format and then their total area per pixel was calculated to express the relationship between hunting pressure and rabbit population decline (IUCN, 2018). Landscape metrics were computed from the correspondence with the LCN scores in Table 1 as mean or sum values per pixel, depending on the type of metric: patch area, core area index, related circumscribing circle, contiguity index, core area, Euclidean nearest-neighbor distance, fractal dimension index, radius of gyration, number of core areas, perimeter-area ratio, perimeter and shape index. Further details on how this type of metrics can be calculated are provided below.

2.2. Dynamics of landscape fragmentation

The patches into which the four land cover groups proposed were divided were determined from 1992 to 2015 using R’s landscapemetrics package (Hesselbarth et al., 2023). This enabled the subsequent calculation of a series of metrics at the patch level. The variety of metrics listed in Table 2 was narrowed down to those listed in Table 3 to obtain a representative and easier-to-interpret sample of the area, edge, core area, shape and aggregation of the patches. The mean per group was computed for all shortlisted metrics, while the sum was also calculated in the case of patch area. In addition, patch density was also calculated as the ratio of the number of patches to the sum of patch area.

The results produced through the analysis of landscape dynamics were evaluated with the support of statistical tools. First, the Mann-Kendall test (Kendall, 1975; Mann, 1945) was applied to the values

Table 3

Shortlisted landscape metrics to provide insight into the dynamics of landscape fragmentation in the study area.

Metric	Description	Type of metric
Patch area (ha)	Area of each patch	Area and edge
Patch density (no. of patches per 100 ha)	Ratio between the number of patches and the total landscape area	Aggregation
Core area index [0–100]	Percentage of each patch that is core area (a cell is core area if it has no neighbor with a different value than itself)	Core area
Contiguity index [0–1]	Spatial connectedness of cells in patches (orthogonally contiguous cells have more weight than diagonally contiguous cells)	Shape
Euclidean nearest-neighbor distance (m)	Distance to the nearest neighboring patch of the same class (patch isolation)	Aggregation
Radius of gyration (m)	Distance from each cell to the patch centroid (patch area and compactness)	Area and edge
Shape index [≥ 1]	Ratio between the actual perimeter of each patch and a hypothetical minimum perimeter of the patch if it would be maximally compact	Shape

obtained concerning both the metrics in Table 3 and the number of patches over the years to determine whether there were upward or downward monotonic trends in the landscape. For a time series x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n of length n , the Mann-Kendall statistic Z_{MK} was calculated as expressed in Eq. (1).

$$Z_{MK} = \begin{cases} \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=k+1}^n \text{sgn}(x_j - x_k) - 1}{\sqrt{\frac{n(n-1)(2n+5) - \sum_{j=1}^p t_j(t_j-1)(2t_j+5)}{18}}}, & \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=k+1}^n \text{sgn}(x_j - x_k) > 0 \\ 0, & \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=k+1}^n \text{sgn}(x_j - x_k) = 0 \\ \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=k+1}^n \text{sgn}(x_j - x_k) + 1}{\sqrt{\frac{n(n-1)(2n+5) - \sum_{j=1}^p t_j(t_j-1)(2t_j+5)}{18}}}, & \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=k+1}^n \text{sgn}(x_j - x_k) < 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $\text{sgn}(x_j - x_k)$ is a function that determines whether the difference between the landscape values at time j and k are positive, zero or negative, p is the number of tied groups in the dataset and t_j is the number of values in the j -th tied group. In addition, the Sen’s slope estimator b_{Sen} was computed to identify the magnitude of the trends identified through Eq. (1) (Sen, 1968). It was calculated as the median from all linear rates of change in the landscape values (Eq. (2)).

$$b_{Sen} = \text{median}\left(\frac{x_j - x_k}{j - k}\right) \quad (2)$$

Fig. 3. Time series trends in the number of patches and sum of patch areas for the land cover groups considered.

Because the power of the Mann-Kendall test depends heavily on the presence of serially correlated data, modified tests should be used to address this issue in trend analysis. In this case, the approaches proposed by Hamed and Ramachandra Rao (1998) and Yue and Wang (2004), respectively, were used. They are both based on variance correction, with the former using only significant lags of the autocorrelation coefficients and the latter resorting to all lags.

In addition, the Kruskal-Wallis (Kruskal and Wallis, 1952) and Dunn's (Dunn, 1964) nonparametric tests were applied to determine if there were differences in landscape metrics over the years. The first was used to analyze the entire time series, while the second served to compare pairs of years. In addition, the results of the Dunn's test were adjusted using the Benjamini-Hochberg to control the false discovery rate (Benjamini and Hochberg, 1995). The level of significance used to determine the strength of statistical evidence in all tests was 0.05. These tests were chosen because equal sample sizes are a requirement for conducting the Friedman test and a paired Mann-Whitney test, which would have been an option for analyzing paired data. Although the data in this case refer to the values of certain metrics over different years, the sample size changes over the years with the number of patches, meaning that the data are not numerically paired.

2.3. Habitat suitability index (HSI)

After the global analysis of landscape dynamics, the usefulness of landscape metrics for deriving a HSI for *Oryctolagus cuniculus* (European rabbit) was investigated. In general, it has been argued that this species prefers to live in open areas of grassland, shrubland, etc. (Lombardi et al., 2007), where refuge areas overlap with others where herbaceous food is plentiful (Monzón et al., 2004). They are also often associated with pasture areas where shrub cover is not very high (e.g., 40% shrub, 35% grassland and 25% bare ground) (Gálvez-Bravo, 2017). In the particular context of the study area (Fig. 2), rabbit abundance has also been observed in irrigated crop areas (Arques et al., 2014).

Consistent with these preferences, landscape metrics for *Oryctolagus cuniculus* were determined for the following ESA CCI land cover codes: 20, 30, 40, 100, 110, 120 (121, 122) and 130 (Table 1). These metrics and the remaining variables included in Table 2 were used as indicators in an MCDA to help identify pixels that are more suitable in terms of habitat for the European rabbit. Therefore, in MCDA terminology, the pixels into which the study area was divided performed as a series of alternatives evaluated against several indicators representing

conflicting criteria.

These alternatives were evaluated using the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) (Hwang and Yoon, 1981), which is a distance-based method that scores said alternatives not only by their closeness to a positive ideal solution in the terms to be evaluated (in this case habitat suitability) but also by their farness from a negative ideal solution. For this purpose, the values x_{ij} of the i alternatives (pixels of the study area) across the j indicators or criteria (variables in Table 2) must first be normalized. This was done using vector normalization, which yielded the normalized values x'_{ij} . These values were then multiplied by the weights w_j of the indicators, representing their relative importance in determining habitat suitability for *Oryctolagus cuniculus*.

The calculation of w_j was posed as an optimization problem where the correlation between the output of the TOPSIS method and the density of European rabbits according to the GBIF records should be maximized. To get to this point, the rest of the TOPSIS method had to be applied first. From the normalized weighted values, the positive (A^+) and negative (A^-) ideal solutions were determined using Eqs. (3) and (4).

$$A^+ = \{(\max_{ij} v_{ij} | j \in J), (\min_{ij} v_{ij} | j \in J), i = 1, 2, \dots, m\} = \{v_1^+, v_2^+, \dots, v_n^+\} \quad (3)$$

$$A^- = \{(\min_{ij} v_{ij} | j \in J), (\max_{ij} v_{ij} | j \in J), i = 1, 2, \dots, m\} = \{v_1^-, v_2^-, \dots, v_n^-\} \quad (4)$$

where J and J stand for benefit and cost indicators in terms of habitat suitability, respectively. The calculation of how close (d_i^+) and far (d_i^-) each pixel in the study area was from A^+ and A^- was carried out using Eqs. (5) and (6).

$$d_i^+ = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_j^+)^2} \quad (5)$$

$$d_i^- = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_j^-)^2} \quad (6)$$

The joint consideration of these distances using Eq. (7) allowed determining the output of the TOPSIS method, i.e., the Relative Closeness (RC_i) of each pixel to an ideal solution with the highest possible HSI. Hence, the higher RC_i , the more suitable a pixel in the study area is as a habitat for *Oryctolagus cuniculus* and vice versa. Although this metric

Table 4

Results of the modified Mann-Kendall test and associated Sen's slope values for the representative landscape metrics and land cover groups considered.

Group	Metric (statistic)	Mann-Kendall	Sen's slope	p-value
Completely artificial	No. of patches	0.956	104.864	0.000
	Patch area (sum)	1.000	2931.557	0.000
	Patch density (no. of patches / patch area (sum))	-0.949	-1239.252	0.000
	Core area index (mean)	0.580	0.037	0.008
	Contiguity index (mean)	0.471	4.569e-04	0.013
	Euclidean nearest-neighbor distance (mean)	-0.920	-6.130	0.000
	Radius of gyration (mean)	0.623	1.557	0.004
	Shape index (mean)	0.587	0.002	0.008
	Transformed system	No. of patches	0.667	76.000
Patch area (sum)		-0.580	-1822.159	0.035
Patch density (no. of patches / patch area (sum))		0.667	143.259	0.013
Core area index (mean)		-0.522	-0.019	0.040
Contiguity index (mean)		-0.732	-0.001	0.002
Euclidean nearest-neighbor distance (mean)		-0.877	-2.179	0.000
Radius of gyration (mean)		-0.652	-2.123	0.011
Shape index (mean)		-0.558	-0.001	0.028
Cultural assisted system		No. of patches	0.004	0.000
	Patch area (sum)	-0.594	-1678.107	0.023
	Patch density (no. of patches / patch area (sum))	0.210	61.906	0.438
	Core area index (mean)	-0.797	-0.024	0.000
	Contiguity index (mean)	-0.891	-0.001	0.000
	Euclidean nearest-neighbor distance (mean)	0.616	0.917	0.001
	Radius of gyration (mean)	-0.696	-1.179	0.003
	Shape index (mean)	-0.065	-7.610e-05	0.768
	Natural and semi-natural	No. of patches	0.351	39.209
Patch area (sum)		0.268	267.750	0.240
Patch density (no. of patches / patch area (sum))		0.138	27.439	0.555
Core area index (mean)		-0.833	-0.098	0.000
Contiguity index (mean)		-0.862	-5.085e-04	0.000
Euclidean nearest-neighbor distance (mean)		-0.728	-0.919	0.002
Radius of gyration (mean)		-0.529	-0.871	0.046
Shape index (mean)		-0.427	-6.696e-04	0.055

also stems from Euclidean distance calculations, it is unrelated to the Euclidean distance-based landscape metric in Table 3. RC_i simply represents a numerical concept of the distance between the HSI values of the pixels in the study area and those of two pixels that were positive and negative ideal in terms of habitat suitability.

$$RC_i = \frac{d_i^-}{d_i^- + d_i^+} \tag{7}$$

As mentioned above, the correlation coefficient between the values of RC_i and the density of European rabbits in 2015 according to the GBIF database was used to determine the weights w_j of the indicators. Specifically, because rabbit density stems from discrete observations, the Spearman correlation coefficient was used to maximize the monotonic association between both sets of values (Spearman, 1904). Therefore, this approach allowed determining which terrain, climate, proximity and landscape variables had a greater influence on the derivation of a HSI.

This whole procedure was solved using two R packages: *topsis* (Yazdi, 2013) and *stats* (R Core Team, 2022). The optimization was performed using the L-BFGS-B method (Byrd et al., 1995), a quasi-Newton approach that can resolve functions with simple constraints. In this case, there were only two constraints to ensure that the weights were positive and not >1 ($0 \leq w_j \leq 1$).

3. Results

3.1. Dynamics of landscape fragmentation

The overall analysis of the landscape in the Valencian Community revealed that the number of patches increased in the four groups into which the land covers in the region were classified based on their naturalness (Fig. 3a). This increase was statistically significant for the first two groups and was particularly pronounced for the Completely artificial, as shown in Table 4, which shows the results of the modified

Mann-Kendall test one according to the approach of Hamed and Ramachandra Rao (1998), which turned out to be the most restrictive. Fig. 3b reveals that despite the area growth of the artificial group (statistically significant and with a Mann-Kendall value of 1), the landscape is dominated by intermediate groups 2 and 3, the extent of which is also higher than that of group 4. Patch area of groups 2 and 3 decreased over time, a trend that remained for group 4, although the loss was not statistically significant according to the Mann-Kendall *p*-value.

Table 4 also includes the results of the modified Mann-Kendall test for the remaining landscape metrics considered in Table 3, while the values used to obtain these results are illustrated in Fig. 4, which presents the observed trends for the metrics examined. In addition, as an example of the distribution and evolution of the four types of landscape metrics considered (area and edge, aggregation, core area and shape), Fig. 5 shows the maps corresponding to the Transformed system for the first and last year within the study period. The results regarding patch density (Fig. 4a) indicated a statistically significant increase for the Transformed system, while the trend was reversed for the Completely artificial group. Although there was a growing trend for the more natural groups, it was not statistically significant according to Table 4.

The results for core area and contiguity followed the same pattern as in Fig. 3b, with a general decreasing trend except for the Completely artificial group. The values observed for this group compared to the others entail increasingly simple patches with larger core areas, as well as larger and higher numbers of connections between the cells that form its patches. Although the trend increased only for group 1, the higher values on these two metrics corresponded to the Transformed system (Fig. 4b and c).

With the exception of the Cultural assisted system, the distance to the nearest neighboring patch of the same group decreased significantly over time for all groups (Table 4). In this case, the highest magnitude of distance values corresponded to the Completely artificial group. The radius of gyration is also based on distances, but from each cell in the patches to their centroids. The only case where this metric increased

Fig. 4. Time series trends in the representative landscape metrics determined for the land cover groups considered.

Fig. 5. Evolution of four representative landscape metrics for the Transformed system land cover group across the study area during the analysis period (1992–2015).

over time was the Completely artificial group (Fig. 4e). This means that group 1 has evolved into less compact and larger patches over time. The results obtained in terms of shape supported this, as artificial patches became more and more complex. Instead, transformed and natural and semi-natural systems tended to have an increasingly square shape. The trend in the Cultural assisted system group on this metric was not statistically significant (Table 4).

The Kruskal-Wallis test revealed that statistically significant differences in certain landscape metrics over the entire analysis period were only found in the intermediate groups: Transformed and Cultural assisted systems (Table 5). The decrease in patch area, contiguity and radius of gyration involved a significant reduction in size, connectedness and elongation, respectively. The Dunn’s test was applied to obtain a more detailed insight into the differences in the landscape for different pairs of years. Table 5 shows that the statistically significant results derived from the test were reduced to the Transformed System and the contiguity index, whereby the trend in recent years points to significantly more disjointed (contiguity) patches. Although the Dunn’s test uses the same data rankings as the Kruskal-Wallis test, the lack of more statistically significant results for other land cover groups and metrics can be attributed to the Benjamini-Hochberg adjustment to reduce false discovery rate.

3.2. Habitat suitability index (HSI)

The data presented in Table 2 were geoprocesed to result in the terrain, climate, proximity and landscape variables sought. As an example of this step, Fig. 6 shows the maps obtained for a subset of the variables considered. Next, statistics per climate pixel were calculated to refer all variables, including European rabbit density, to the same spatial scale. All variables were expressed as means per pixel, except for rabbit density, hunting area and patch area, for which their sum per pixel was determined.

As an exploratory analysis before applying the MCDA methodology to derive a HSI, a Spearman correlation matrix was calculated as shown in Fig. 7. The relationship between rabbit density (denoted as rabbit in Fig. 7) and the remaining variables was statistically significant in all cases except for interpatch distance. The correlation coefficients were negative for distance to roads (−0.39), slope (−0.14), hunting areas (−0.12) and precipitation (−0.27), whereas they were positive for maximum temperature (0.52), soil permeability (0.13) and all landscape metrics. The strongest correlations for the latter were found for core area (0.45), perimeter (0.44) and radius of gyration (0.42).

Insight into the relationships between rabbit density and the variables considered in the HSI helped in the application of the TOPSIS method. After normalization, the next step was to determine the positive and negative ideal solutions, which required knowing whether the variables were cost or benefit indicators. The signs in Fig. 7 indicated this, so that positive correlation coefficients entailed benefit indicators, and vice versa for negative correlations. Applying the remaining steps of the TOPSIS method, including the step where the weights of the indicators were calculated as a maximization problem, produced the results in Fig. 8.

The optimization step also served as a dimensionality reduction process, since a weight of zero was assigned to the indicators whose relevance was reduced to maximize agreement with the records in Fig. 2b. As a result, only eight indicators, as shown in Fig. 8a, were found to be important enough to derive a HSI for European rabbits. The maximum temperature in the area and the related circumscribing circle of the patches were by far the two most important indicators and reached a weight of 0.38 each. The remaining indicators had a weight below 0.10 in all cases, with precipitation (0.09) and distance to roads (0.05) being the next most contributing variables.

The fit of the values of RC_i obtained using these weights to the observations of *Oryctolagus cuniculus* is depicted in Fig. 8b and Fig. 8c. The Spearman correlation coefficient between both sets of values was 0.72,

Table 5

Results of the Kruskal-Wallis and Dunn's tests (using the Benjamini-Hochberg procedure) for the representative landscape metrics and land cover groups considered. Only statistically significant results (p -value < 0.05) are shown. "Test statistic" accounts for the chi-square and Z statistics for the Kruskal Wallis and Dunn's tests, respectively.

Group	Test	Metric	Years	Test statistic	p-value
Transformed system	Kruskal-Wallis test	Area	All	43.557	0.010
		Contiguity index	All	50.770	0.001
		Radius of gyration	All	36.047	0.041
	Dunn's test	Contiguity index	1999 vs 2012	2.627	0.044
			2000 vs 2012	2.626	0.043
			1992 vs 2013	2.628	0.046
			1993 vs 2013	2.643	0.049
			1994 vs 2013	2.528	0.050
			1995 vs 2013	2.619	0.042
			2001 vs 2013	2.561	0.047
			1992 vs 2014	2.702	0.048
			1993 vs 2014	2.716	0.048
			1994 vs 2014	2.602	0.043
			1995 vs 2014	2.693	0.047
			2001 vs 2014	2.634	0.047
			1994 vs 2015	2.636	0.048
2001 vs 2015	2.668	0.048			
Cultural assisted system	Kruskal-Wallis	Contiguity index	All	54.623	0.000

indicating a moderate to strong association (Schober et al., 2018). According to the HSI, the more suitable habitats are in the central part of the region, not very far and not very close to the coast in the east. Instead, the less suitable habitats (lowest values of RC_i) are concentrated in the north-western part of the Valencian Community, which coincides with more mountainous areas. Considering the importance of temperature (Fig. 8a) and the spatial distribution of this variable (Fig. 6), these results suggest that rabbits prefer warm areas. Fig. 8c also agrees with Fig. 5, which presents the spatial distribution of several landscape metrics for the Transformed system, which includes some of the preferred habitats for rabbits such as croplands and mosaics of natural vegetation. The patterns in Fig. 5 show larger and more contiguous patches in the areas where rabbits are more abundant, and the opposite in the zones where rabbits are less common (Fig. 8).

4. Discussion

4.1. Changes in landscape metrics over time

The first objective of this research was to examine the trends in landscape dynamics according to the degree of naturalness of the land cover. In this sense, the evolution of patch density suggests a fragmentation of the landscape for the Transformed system, while the Completely artificial group was significantly less fragmented over time. The growing trend for the more natural covers suggested fragmentation, but this was not statistically significant. To identify possible reasons for the patterns in the number of patches, patch area and patch density, other landscape metrics were examined.

Consistent with the patch density results, the trends found in contiguity confirm that the increasing number of patches observed for the Completely artificial group is not caused by fragmentation of existing patches, but rather by the presence of more and larger artificial surfaces. This might cause a fragmentation in the remaining groups, whose core area and contiguity have been reduced over time. Recent territorial planning analyses conducted in the metropolitan area of Valencia, the capital of the Valencian Community, coincided in revealing that natural and agricultural areas are more fragmented due to the spread of urbanized and artificial areas (Miralles I Garcia, 2019; Valera Lozano et al., 2019). A recent global study found that high levels of anthropogenic landscape fragmentation were also found for European countries such as Germany, France or England, while these were notably lower for other regions such as the United States, probably due to the lower urban center to total area ratio and the presence of regions with low population (Romanillos et al., 2024).

The increased sum area in the Completely artificial group might be derived from urbanization processes related to the Spanish housing bubble between 1997 and 2006 (Burriel, 2016), which could also be behind the anomalies in the number of patches found for the intermediate groups over this period. This is in line with the conclusions of Membrado (2012), who analyzed patterns in land cover data in the Valencian Community and found a growth in land occupied for residential purposes and a decline in less developed areas. This change in the real estate market spread across the world, eventually leading to the bubble bursting in 2008 (Duca et al., 2010).

This urbanization process also favors rural depopulation, which in turn has resulted in the abandonment of crop areas and pastures in the region (Jato-Espino and Mayor-Vitoria, 2023). In a similar vein, Pawlewicz and Pawlewicz (2023) pointed out that rural exodus is one of the causes of agricultural land abandonment in the European Union, with Spain being among the most vulnerable countries and more economically developed countries such as Belgium, Denmark and the Netherlands being more resilient to this phenomenon. The abandonment of agricultural areas leads to their colonization of such areas by forests and other natural areas, which may explain the decline observed in the Transformed system in favor of more natural and semi-natural areas. The particularly notable rise in area observed in the latter group between 1999 and 2001 could be due to the major fires that occurred during those years in the Valencian Community, successively destroying an average of 6000 ha per year (Zambon et al., 2019). The magnitude of these consecutive events encouraged aerial reforestation efforts in subsequent years (El País, 2000), which might also potentially support the rise in the area of this land cover group.

The identified trends in patch shape are also consistent with previous analyses, as the increasing complexity and length of patches in the Completely artificial group coincides with the type of urbanization reported in the region. It was diffuse and characterized by low building density, which contradicted the concept of a compact city (Membrado, 2012). This is consistent with the review of Bin Sulaiman (2023), who found that most of the scientific production on compact cities over the past 50 years came from China, United Kingdom, the United States, Australia and Japan, with Spain having a much more discrete contribution. The increasing presence, elongation and irregularity observed in the patches in the most developed group may have led to fragmentation in the remaining groups, which have become more compact and squarer over the years.

The fact that the Cultural assisted system was the only group that showed an increasing trend in terms of distance between patches might be due to the characteristics of this group, which includes mixed land

Fig. 6. Spatial distribution of the values of a subset of the climate, terrain, proximity and landscape indicators considered for the development of a Habitat Suitability Index (HSI).

Fig. 7. Correlation matrix indicating the strength and direction of the relationship between the variables involved in the development of a Habitat Suitability Index (HSI). Cells marked with an “x” indicate correlation coefficients that are not statistically significant.

covers (natural vegetation and cropland) with moderate to high vegetation diversity. Therefore, they are open spaces and transition zones between transformed systems and natural and semi-natural areas that might have been more affected by the increase in medium to large infrastructure developments. Reversing this trend can be a key aspect in changing the landscape dynamics observed in the region, as these types

Fig. 8. (a) Optimized weights of the important variables to create a Habitat Suitability Index (HSI) (b) Scatter plot showing the correlation between the Relative Closeness (RC_i) values of the HSI and the observed density of *Oryctolagus cuniculus* and (c) Spatial distribution of the values of RC_i across the study area.

of open spaces are suitable for carrying out ecological restoration measures (Yang et al., 2014). In line with the EU Green Infrastructure Strategy (EEA, 2023), the Valencian Community has been a pioneering

region of Spain in developing a green infrastructure planning strategy to bring together natural and man-made systems. This strategy was implemented precisely in 2015 in the capital of the study area (Martí et al., 2020). Generating spatial information on landscape metrics can be of benefit to decision-makers by gaining insight into the fragmentation of certain land covers and thus foster the development of strategies and measures to improve their connectivity such as wildlife crossings. In addition, the availability of maps showing the spatial distribution of landscape metrics can support the development of Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) procedures so that infrastructure projects and plans are tailored to maintain landscape connectivity.

4.2. Significant variables for deriving a habitat suitability index (HSI)

The land cover types included in the Cultural assisted system were also the main preferred landscape options for *Oryctolagus cuniculus* (European rabbit), whose modelling in terms of habitat suitability was the second objective of the research. The use of HSI based on the combination of GIS and MCDA for this purpose has been recommended in the literature for different areas and animal species (Carvalho et al., 2012; Lebert et al., 2022; Reza et al., 2013). In the case of the European rabbit, habitat suitability approaches were developed using generalized linear models (Carvalho and Gomes, 2003; Fernández, 2005). Compared to MCDA methods, these models and others such as species distribution models are computationally and interpretively more demanding and do not necessarily lead to significantly better results (Khalil et al., 2022). In addition, MCDA methods are characterized by their adaptability, allowing them to be applied to a wide range of areas (Taherdoost and Madanchian, 2023) and thus enabling more holistic strategies to improve spatial planning, including natural spaces and their associated ecosystem services (Bousquet et al., 2023).

The spatial characterization of the indicators proposed to derive the HSI led to logical associations with rabbit abundance. The obtained strong positive correlation with maximum temperature does not mean that rabbits prefer extremely hot conditions, but rather that they avoid harsh winter conditions (Rödel et al., 2004). Comparatively, these adverse conditions occur more in the mountainous northwest of the region. In general, rabbit abundance in Spain is directly related to temperature and inversely related to precipitation (Delibes-Mateos and Villafuerte, 2018), which is consistent with the findings of this study and also with trends in other regions with different weather conditions, such as Germany and Australia (Rödel, 2000; Scanlan et al., 2006). However, it is traditionally argued that this pattern changes in Mediterranean areas due to the positive effects of rainfall on the growth of plant species and therefore on food availability (Calvete et al., 2006). This trend might have changed in recent years because of the increasing pressure of climate change, which is causing extreme storms in the Valencian Community, the magnitude of which is more likely to destroy plants and crops.

The positive correlation found with soil lies in the importance of soil softness for digging burrows, which is essential for reproduction and protection from predators and extreme climate conditions (Calvete et al., 2004). Furthermore, this circumstance also explains the observed negative correlation of distance to roads. The rabbits' preference for proximity to roads has been reported in several investigations in Spain (Gea-Izquierdo et al., 2005; Tapia et al., 2014), highlighting the suitability of road embankments for building burrows and the safety of roadsides for breeding (Bautista et al., 2004). The importance of these parameters has also been reported in other parts of the world. A study in Australia stressed the positive effects of soft geological layers (deposits and limestone) on rabbit abundance, as well as other variables such as terrain roughness and wetness (Jansen et al., 2023). These authors also point out the advantages of a previously ripped terrain, the looseness of which could be caused by earthmoving work to prepare the roadside.

The most intuitive association found between the landscape metrics remaining in the HSI was that of core area, as large and rather compact

patches in the rabbits' preferred habitats should encourage their presence. This factor has been argued to be more important for small mammal abundance than other landscape variables (Delibes-Mateos et al., 2009). Apparently, the core area results might be in contrast to those of the related circumscribing circle and fractal dimension index, as these suggest that rabbit abundance is positively correlated with more linear and irregular patches. However, the results showed that the latter two metrics were positively correlated with core area (0.60 and 0.87, respectively), indicating that high values of core area did not necessarily imply a tendency toward patch compactness and squareness. This trend is in contrast to the findings of Dellafiore et al. (2008), where the number of rabbit warrens was negatively correlated with the perimeter-area ratio. This metric is analogous to the fractal dimension index, except that unlike the latter, it is not scale-independent, meaning that the ratio changes as the patch size is increased without changing the patch shape. Furthermore, the divergence between both studies may also lie in the different spatial-temporal analysis scales. This research was based on the 300 m pixel ESA CCI land cover data from 2015, while the work by Dellafiore et al. (2008) used warren observations from 110 parallel belt transects with a width of 10 m created in 2003 and spaced 100 m apart. Something similar emerges when examining the results of Narce et al. (2012), who used transect counts from six pilot areas to measure rabbit abundance in southeastern France. This could explain the partial agreement between both studies, because although the fractal dimension was one of the landscape metrics that turned out to be statistically significant in our case, its importance was almost negligible, which is in contrast to its primary role along with interspersions in theirs.

Although the results obtained are generally consistent with the information reported in the study area and the literature, the data used represent precisely the main limitation that may affect the scope of the results obtained in this research. Landscape dynamics were analyzed using open data with a rather coarse spatial granularity. Although the study area is large enough, finer data would have been desirable for the sake of accuracy. Regarding the HSI, the low resolution of the land cover data adds to the fact that the GBIF records used to determine the occurrence of the European rabbit stem from a non-systematic sampling of observations. Therefore, field data would be recommended for further validation of the obtained results.

The findings of this study feed into the Valencian Community's Biodiversity Strategy, published in mid-2022 with the aim of achieving 50% protection of ecosystems and habitats in the region by 2030 (Conselleria de Medio Ambiente, Infraestructuras y Territorio, 2022). In fact, the Valencian Community is one of the richest regions in Spain in terms of biodiversity, having managed its own Biodiversity Data Bank since 2003 and contributing up to 2,619,112 records to the GBIF database (Conselleria de Medio Ambiente, Infraestructuras y Territorio, 2024). Building models that indicate which factors determine the presence of species in the region can guide preservation efforts, assist in locating hotspots and promote the implementation of adaptive management of natural and seminatural areas (Climate-ADAPT, 2022). Current map viewers showing the distribution of species might be enhanced by displaying the patterns of related climate, landscape and infrastructure variables to provide a more comprehensive picture of the spatial context of the area, which would have a dual effect: improving ecological education and helping make more informed decisions.

5. Conclusions

This study demonstrated the usefulness of landscape metrics to both provide insight into spatiotemporal landscape fragmentation and to help build a HSI to determine animal species abundance. It was found that the use of land cover data classified according to their naturalness led to a representative portrait of landscape dynamics in the Valencian Community (Eastern Spain), while their subsequent combination with terrain, climate and proximity variables resulted in accurate estimates of European rabbit (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) density.

Analysis of landscape dynamics revealed an increasing presence of artificial land cover in terms of area, proximity and contiguity, leading to fragmentation of less transformed areas. In addition, over the years, a replacement of crop areas with natural and semi-natural spaces has been observed, while the patches in open spaces based on mixed land covers (vegetation and arable land) were found to be increasingly spaced apart. In this sense, an opportunity was identified to carry out restoration measures for this type of land covers. The use of green infrastructure and green corridors emerges as an option for this purpose.

The results provided by the HSI, based on the coupling of GIS and MCDA, were highly concordant with the observed patterns of rabbit density in the region. The most important variables in obtaining these estimates were the maximum temperature, as the rabbits try to avoid extreme climate conditions, and the related circumscribing circle, a shape landscape metric that characterizes the compactness of the patches. Accordingly, the more suitable habitats corresponded to the central part of the study area, at a reasonable distance from the coast and away from the mountains, where transition zones in the form of mixed land covers, such as those preferred by this rabbit species, can be found.

The spatial distribution of landscape metrics determined for different land cover groups according to their naturalness, as well as the achieved HSI values, provide valuable information for the design of planning strategies to balance future human developments with the protection of habitats and biodiversity. The potential of the proposed methods to locate especially sensitive areas in terms of landscape fragmentation and/or habitat unsuitability may contribute to achieving the targets of international initiatives on biodiversity and ecosystem safeguard, such as the fifteenth Sustainable Development Goal (SDG). In particular, these results can support the strategic implementation of specific ecological connectivity restoration practices such as wildlife crossings, which can be effective in both respects.

To facilitate the use of the tools developed here by non-experts in their underlying methods, future efforts should be directed toward automating them as web applications so that users would only need to make a few open data entries to achieve the desired results. Given the software environment used in the present study, Shiny would be the suggested option for this. Other potential lines of research to be developed include testing the proposed methods under different conditions in terms of land development and selected mammals as target species.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Daniel Jato-Espino: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Sophie Lierow:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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